

A TEST TO ANALYSE THE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITES AND THEIR ASSEMBLIES UNDER OUT-OF-PLANE LOADINGS

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SUMMARY

This paper describes the use of a modified Arcan test to determine the behaviour of composites and hybrid bonded assemblies under a large range of radial out-of-plane loadings. The key advantage of this fixture is to strongly limit the influence of edge effects. Through-thickness reinforcement (z-pins) is also evaluated.

Keywords: Composite, Out-of-plane loadings, Adhesion, Z-pins, Non-linear behaviour, Finite element analysis

CONTEXT

The use of adhesive bonding has developed considerably in recent years and the pressing requirement for lighter weight in all areas of transportation to reduce energy consumption will inevitably result in more applications. Composite materials are a key element in weight reduction strategies, so assembly of composite modules and connections between composite and metallic structures are of great importance. Few of the standard adhesive tests are suitable to characterize such composite assemblies. As a result, the lack of appropriate tests may be considered to be one of the factors currently limiting adhesive bonding for structural applications [1, 2].

Failure initiation in bonded assemblies involving composites is often associated with crack initiation in the adhesive or delamination of the composite plies close to the adhesive joint. However, few experimental devices are proposed in the literature to characterise the mechanical behaviour of composites under out-of-plane loadings [3-5]; those available often use thick composite specimens, not representative of the application, (Iosipescu type tests [6]) or require special geometries [4,5]. Different geometries are also needed to obtain the values required for a tension-shear failure envelope. There has been some work in the past on the so-called Arcan test fixture [7] to obtain tensile-shear data [8], but the machining of the composite, the geometry of the

specimen, the fixing system, ... can lead to large scatter in the experimental results. In order to obtain experimental results representative of industrial applications, there is a need on the one hand to use composite plates with quite low thicknesses, which are easy to manufacture, and on the other hand to apply a range of tensile-shear loadings. In order to respect those conditions, a modified Arcan type device, using adhesive as the fixing system is proposed here, to analyse the mechanical behaviour of both bonded assemblies including composites and the behaviour of the composites themselves under out-of-plane loadings. Different numerical studies have been developed in order to analyse and optimize the design of such a system (geometry of the composite plate, geometry of the substrates, fixing system, ...). In order to obtain reliable experimental results, it is essential to limit the influence of edge effects. Some test results are presented which underline the potential of this approach.

ANALYSIS OF THE NON LINEAR BEHAVIOR OF BONDED JOINTS

In a previous study a modified Arcan fixture, which allows compression or tension to be combined with shear loads, was designed in order to define an experimental methodology enabling the adhesives of interest to be characterized up to failure [9].

(a) Modified Arcan fixture (shear loading)

1 - support of the Arcan fixture
 2 - bonded specimen
 3 - clamping system
 4 - support of the clamping system
 (b) Mounting of the specimen

(c) Geometry of the substrates

(d) Geometry of the bonded assembly

Figure 1. Arcan fixture and geometry of the substrates with beaks

It has been shown numerically that the use of a beak close to the adhesive joint makes it possible to limit the contribution of the singularities due to edge effects, and that the geometry of the joint close to the edge is an important parameter. This experimental

fixture allows, for radial tensile-shear loadings, the non-linear behaviour of an adhesive joint to be analyzed [9] and thus to develop precise numerical models to describe the behaviour of an adhesive in an assembly [10].

ANALYSIS OF HYBRID BONDED ASSEMBLIES

Presentation of the experimental device

The first tests performed using hybrid bonded assemblies (steel, aluminium and composites) have shown a similar behaviour to that of the adhesive, using the proposed procedure [19]. Different studies have shown that large stress singularities, associated with edge effects, can exist for bi-material structures. For bonded assemblies involving composites those effects can limit the transmitted load considerably. The adhesive-composite interface influences the assembly strength, and makes it difficult to analyse the behaviour of composites under out-of-plane loadings [8]. The fixture proposed here to analyse the behaviour of hybrid bonded assemblies with composites is presented in figure 2. A composite plate is bonded between the two metallic substrates. The area of the bonded section is $65 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ and a special alignment fixture is used in order to obtain a good quality of the geometry of the bonded specimen (Figure 2a).

Figure 2. Experimental fixture with hybrid bonded assembly.

Parameters of the numerical models

The experimental procedure based on the modified Arcan device can be used in order to analyse the behaviour of a metal-adhesive-composite-adhesive-metal assembly. In order to analyse and optimise this experimental device, a precise analysis of the stress distribution through the thickness of the adhesive joint and through the composite is necessary. Various 2D stress plane computations have been performed using refined meshes, in order to obtain a precise estimation of the influence of the edge effects. For the adhesive and the composite, 20 linear elements were used for a thickness of 0.1 mm. For this study, unidirectional carbon-epoxy composites (fibres in direction x, figure 2b); these allow the use of orthotropic models ($E_1=110 \text{ GPa}$, $E_2=6.5 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12}=6.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.32$) and the elastic limit is chosen such that:

$$\frac{\sigma_{xy}^2}{R_c^2} + \frac{\sigma_{yy}^2}{S_c^2} + \frac{\sigma_{xx}^2}{T_c^2} = 1 \quad \text{with } R_c = 52 \text{ MPa, } S_c = 16 \text{ MPa and } T_c = 1600 \text{ MPa}$$

$\rho = \infty, h = 0.4 \text{ mm} \& H = 4 \text{ mm}$

$\rho = 0.75 * h, h = 0.4 \text{ mm} \& H = 4 \text{ mm}$

$\rho = 0.75 * h, h = 0.2 \text{ mm} \& H = 1 \text{ mm}$

Adhesive

Composite

Figure 3. Normalized equivalent stress distribution of the adhesive and the composite under tension-shear loadings (substrates without beaks, $d = 0$ and $D = 0$).

The behaviour of the adhesive (Redux 420) is assumed to be isotropic ($E_j = 2.0 \text{ GPa}$,

possible to normalize the results in order to simplify the analysis of the results; thus the equivalent stress is normalised to 1 at the centre of the composite. Those results (Figure 3) underline that large stress gradients exist close to the ends of the adhesive and the composite plate. The cleaning of the free edges of the adhesive and the reduction of the thickness of the adhesive joint and of the composite only allow a reduction of the influence of the edge effects. In order to strongly limit the stress concentrations at the periphery of the useful part of the specimen, two modifications of the geometry of the bonded specimen have been proposed: the machining of beaks on the substrates ($\alpha = 45^\circ$, $r_0 = 0.8$ mm and $d = 0.5$ mm, figure 2) [9] and the use of a composite plate larger than the substrates ($D = 2$ mm) in order to limit the effects of machining [8]. Results presented in Figure 4 show that the use of thin adhesive joints and thin composite plates allows us to define a “reliable” experimental device. A system which ensures a maximal stress state in the centre of the useful part of the specimen also allows the influence of machining and positioning defects of specimens to be reduced. It is important to note that for a tensile-shear loading the elastic limit is reached first in the composite. An optimisation of the choice of the adhesive has to be performed, especially for shear loadings; in fact, the shear strength of the composite can be higher than the shear strength of the adhesive. The use of very thin adhesive increases the strength of the adhesive joint.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Unidirectional composites

Unidirectional (UD) carbon/epoxy composites have been used to validate the proposed test. Adhesive joints with a thickness of 0.2 mm have been used to limit the edge effect. We denote by DN and DT the relative displacements of the two substrates respectively in the normal and tangential directions in the mean plane of the composite plate. FN and FT are the components of the applied load respectively in the normal and tangential directions in the mean plane of the composite plate.

Figure 5. Experimental results for shear loadings & Section through the specimen, with failure at the lower adhesive/aluminium interface (scale graduations 0.5 mm).

Figure 5 presents experimental results for shear loading tests (results from two specimens are presented: Comp1 and Comp2). For those tests failure of the adhesive occurs close to the adhesive-substrate interface, as predicted by the numerical analyses. Figure 5 also presents the experimental result for a test without the composite but with a

joint thickness of 0.4 mm (a bonded aluminium/aluminium joint). It can be noted that the global behaviour of the two types of test are quite similar, in fact the most loaded part of the assembly is the adhesive. But when the composite plate is included there are four interfaces compared to only two without the composite plate. Figure 6 shows results for tensile tests, for which fracture occurs within the composite plate. Experiments in which the composite was replaced by an aluminium plate (with nearly the same thickness) make it possible to estimate the deformation of the composite plate. Figure 7 presents results for tensile-shear loading tests which are also associated with fracture in the composite. Tests in which the composite plate was replaced by an aluminium plate (with similar thickness) make it possible estimate the deformation of the composite plate. Similar results to those from the shear tests are observed.

Figure 6. Experimental results for tensile loadings & Section through a specimen, failure within the composite.

Figure 7. Experimental results for tensile-shear loadings

Comparison of different composites

Following the development of the modified Arcan test on unidirectional composites the test has been applied to a number of more realistic sequences used in industrial applications in a boatyard environment. Different composite plates, manufactured at the same time, in an autoclave with metal plates on both faces in order to obtain similar surfaces, have been analyzed (Table 1). These composites are stronger than the previous ones, so thinner adhesive joints have been used (0.1 mm). The relative normal displacement DN is measured with an extensometer in order to obtain accurate values. It is important to note that the maximum value of DN is quite low. DN includes the

deformation of a part of the aluminium substrates, the deformation of the two adhesive joints and the deformation of the composite plate.

Table 1. Properties of different composites tested

G : Glass satin prepreg 1454/49%/300g/m²
 C1 : Carbon 0/90° prepreg G0803/M10/42%/3K/285g/m²
 C2 : Carbon UD prepreg UD/M40J/R367-2/38%/300g/m²

	A		B		C		D		E	
Ply n°	Fibre	Angle	Fibre	Angle	Fibre	Angle	Fibre	Angle	Fibre	Angle
1	G	+/-45°	G	+/-45°	G	+/-45°	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°
2	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°	C2	0°	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°
3	C1	+/-45°	C2	90°	C2	0°	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°
4	C1	+/-45°	C2	90°	C2	0°	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°
5	G	+/-45°	C2	0°	C2	0°	C1	+/-45°	C2	0°
6			G	+/-45°	G	+/-45°			C2	0°
Thickness	1.64 mm		1.96 mm		1.94 mm		1.64 mm		1.90 mm	

Composite D

Composite A (after failure)

Results for all materials

Composite B (after failure)

Figure 8. Analysis of different composites under tension loadings.

Figure 8 presents some experimental results. The scatter in the experimental results is quite low for tests on mixed bonded assemblies with composites when experimental conditions are carefully controlled, as shown by the reproducibility of results from three tests on material D. Figure 8 shows that there is an influence of the geometrical properties of the composite on the damage development and failure behaviour under out-of-plane loadings. Figure 8 also presents the composite after failure, it is important to note that failure is observed within the composite, not in the adhesive nor at the

composite surface, in all cases. These results confirm that the modified Arcan test is able to analyse the behaviour of hybrid bonded assemblies with composites under tensile-shear loadings. Experimental results show that the fibre orientations, the characteristics of different plies and the surface preparation all have an influence on the out-of-plane strength of the composite. Based on this approach it is possible to optimize the strength of hybrid bonded assemblies for a particular loading. More work is underway to clarify the role of composite damage mechanisms in mixed joint performance. Additional results can be found in [12].

Influence of through-thickness reinforcement (z-pinning)

New material developments such as through-thickness reinforcements offer great potential for improving joint efficiency [13]. Selective use of pins in highly-stressed regions can limit damage development, and prevent the delamination mechanism shown in Figure 8. However, unless more effort is directed towards the characterization of these new systems they will remain under-exploited. Characterization of such systems is not simple, as any mechanism to limit damage development in the composite will result in high loads on the adhesive and the composite/adhesive interface. The adhesive layer must then be very thin and the surface preparation of the composite plates is then primordial; special machining techniques are needed to avoid damaging the surface near protruding pin ends. A first series of tests has been performed to examine the behaviour of pinned composites. Figure 9 shows a sample before and after tensile test. Failure no longer occurs within the composite, but premature damage at the composite/adhesive interface has prevented characterization of the full benefits of this technology. Further tests with alternative bonding strategies are underway.

Figure 9. Pinned composite sample before and after test.

CONCLUSION

Numerical and experimental results indicate that the modified Arcan test fixture is suitable for obtaining the response of hybrid bonded assemblies (metal-adhesive-composite-adhesive-metal) provided certain conditions are respected to limit the influence of edge effects: i.e. thin composite plates, substrates with beaks, thin adhesive layer with cleaned free edges. This test allows the mechanical behaviour of both composites and hybrid metal/composite bonded assemblies to be analysed under tensile-shear out-of-plane loadings. An optimization of the adhesive must be performed, especially under shear loadings, as the shear strength of the composite can be higher than that of the adhesive. Experimental results show that the fibre orientations, the characteristics of different plies and the surface preparation all have an influence on the out-of-plane strength of the composite. This study makes it possible to optimize the strength of hybrid bonded assemblies. Moreover, the influence of through-thickness

reinforcement (z-pinning) on the behaviour of composites under out-of-plane loadings can be studied.

More work is underway to clarify the role of composite damage mechanisms in mixed joints. In order to characterize the damage evolution in the composite under out-of-plane loadings, appropriate measurement techniques are being developed, in order to analyze very small displacements. Moreover inverse procedures must also be developed in order to take into account the non-linear behaviour of the adhesive [10] and of the composite [14], as the stress state is not homogeneous for the proposed test.

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